

In-House Communication Patterns on Job Satisfaction of Library Staff: A Case Study of Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri Nigeria

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Abstract: The study focused on influence of in-house communication patterns on job satisfaction of library staff. The descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study covered the entire population of 73 library staff. The questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. The finding shows that memo has no influence on job satisfaction of library staff. That newsletter and intercom have influence on job satisfaction of library staff. The study recommends that memo as an in-house communication pattern need to be reengineered for job satisfaction of library staff while further study is necessary to establish the reason/s behind low performance of memo as an in-house communication pattern.

Keywords: Influence, Communication Patterns, Job Satisfaction, Library Staff, Nigeria

Introduction

Communication can take various forms but all forms involve the transfer of information from one party to another. In order for the transfer of information to qualify as communication, the recipient must understand the meaning of the information transferred to him. If the recipient does not understand the meaning of the information conveyed to him, communication has not taken place. Communication is the life source of any organization because organization involves people. People cannot interact with each other without communication. In the absence of communication in an organization everything will be grinded to a halt.

According to Adair (2010), without communication in an organization, workers in an organization would not know the organization's objectives, so they would not strive to achieve the objectives. The author maintained that the workers in an organization would not know what the roles and responsibilities are, so they would not be able to carry out their daily task and duties. Managers will not be able to train their workers, which means the workers will not possess the skills needed to carry out their jobs. Furthermore,

they will not be able to inform workers of changes; even the organization would not be aware of their competitor's activities. On the whole, people are able to communicate with each other as this is a basic human function. However, successful organizations strive not only for communication, but for effective communication.

In-house communication is defined as communication which occurs through the official organizational channels or is undertaken by an employee to do his job. For example official meetings, letters and managers asking an employee to carry out a particular task. Conversely, informal communication is that communication which occurs outside the recognized communication networks such as talking in the lunchroom or hallways between employees. Informal communication can be productive or unproductive. It has the potential to build team, improve working relationships and generate ideas as employees are in a relaxed environment, (Himmicks, 2010).

Internal Organizational Communication is a communication that takes place within or across an

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organization. In addition to the usual face to face, telephone, fax or mail; modern organizations may use technology to communicate internally. Technology may be used for email or a link internal communication system such as the intranet which is an internet system designed solely for use by those working for the organization. Conversely, external communication is communication between the organization and those outside the organization. Modern organizations may design technological system so that they can communicate with customers and undertake e-commerce. Alternatively, they communicate with other business through the internet or similar system and undertake e-business. Technology has rapidly expanded the types of internal and external communication available to organizations. Combined together, internal and external types of communication allow various sectors of the local, national and international community to interact liaise and conduct business (Max 1997).

Organizations may engage in upward or downward communication. Downward communications are communication created by directors and managers and passed down the hierarchy of the organization. In traditional organizations, this is the preferred method of communication, i.e. manager decides the systems, rules and procedure and then pass these down to the employees they manage and supervise. Downward communication can increase efficiency by synchronizing procedures and can ensure that everybody is working towards the same aims and objectives. Types of downward communication include, job descriptions appraisal/evaluation, organization policy, and organizational system. Although there are advantages to downward communication, organizations are beginning to encourage upward communication which may increase motivation and make employees feel valued and respected whilst enabling managers to understand how employees are feeling. Upward communications include suggestions scheme, feedback forums/surveys, grievance procedures and employee manager discussions (Agarwal, 2014).

Hornby (2006) defines satisfaction as the rate at which a worker, a company or a country enjoys the turnover of goods and services at the amount produced, compared with how much time, work and money needed to produce them. This definition implies that satisfaction is measurable or quantifiable. We may therefore have relative cases such as low, improved, increased or decreased satisfaction. Hornby (2006) further describes a job as a work for which one receives regular payment and the word 'satisfactory' as the good feeling that you have when something that you wanted to happen does happen.

Job satisfaction therefore implies the pleasant emotional state of fulfillment derived by workers in an employment, when the conditions within their organization suits their personal expectations. The extent to which library staff are influenced by in-house communication patterns towards job satisfaction motivated this research.

Literature Review

According to Thomas (2012), in-house communication is a process of transmitting information between different parts of an organization. It is one of the basic functions of management in any organization. For communication with the outside world, organizations use advertising materials, news releases and audio visual aids. However, for communication within organization and with employees, different forms of communications are used such as in-house magazine, memo, intercom, newsletter, query and workshop to transmit ideas, thoughts and information.

Memo writing is something of an art form, as a letter is not a memo, nor is a memo a letter. A memo is a short, to the point communication conveying your thoughts, reactions or opinions on something. According to Newman (2013), memo can call people to action or broadcast a bit of timely news, as with all writing, memo writing needs a structure because they are short, if not, it will destroy the memo's effectiveness and become a waste of productive time to those that read it and to the person who wrote it. If you have something longer than a page, it is better to send it as an attachment or a document that follows the memo used as a cover letter. Never make a memo too long. If someone takes a glance at a memo that appears to be too long, there's a good chance it will be set aside for a time when they are not busy. This can defeat your memo's purpose which is timely communication. A memorandum which is abbreviated as memo can have only a certain number of formats.

According to Pearsall and Cook (2009), a memo may have a format specific to an office or institution. In law specifically, a memorandum is a record of the terms of a transaction or contract, such as a policy memo, memorandum of understanding, memorandum of agreement, or memorandum of association. Alternative formats include memos, briefing notes, reports, letters or binders. They could be one page long or many. They may be considered as grey literature, if the user is a cabinet minister or a senior executive, the format might be rigidly defined and limited to one or two pages. If the user is a colleague, the format is usually more flexible. At its most basic level, a memorandum can be a handwritten note to one's supervisor. In business, a memo is typically used by firms for internal

communication, as opposed to letters which are typically for external communications. Hence, we can consider memoranda as an upward communication process through which complaints; issues, opinions, views and suggestions are put forward to the authorized level.

Newsletter is a brief report, especially an official statement on a matter of public interest issued for immediate publication or broadcast. It is a brief update or summary of current news, as on television or radio or in a newspaper. It could be periodical, especially one published by an organization or society and could also be a printed programme, (Bear, 2017). According to Archard (2014), newsletter is a pamphlet-type regular or irregular periodical issued by an institution or other organization usually for announcements or news. A newsletter is a regularly distributed publication that is generally about one main topic of interest to its subscribers. Newspapers and leaflets are types of newsletters. For example, newsletters are distributed at schools to inform parents about things that happen in that school. In the words of Anderson (2014), newsletters are published by clubs, churches, societies, associations, and libraries to provide information of interest to members, customers, users or employees. A newsletter may be considered as grey literature.

Intercom is a stand-alone voice communications system for use within a building or small collection of buildings, functioning independently of the public telephone network. Intercoms are generally mounted permanently in buildings and vehicles. Intercoms can incorporate connections to public address loudspeaker systems, Walkie-talkie, telephones, and to other intercom systems. Some intercom systems incorporate control of devices such as signal lights and door latches (Bolinder, 2011).

Wilson (2013) opines that an office intercom is useful for any business owner, whether they have regular visitors or they are a closed site as one can choose from a variety of options, including buzzer, swipe card or with a PIN code, or opt for an ultra-modern biometric lock with an intercom built in. Whatever the size of the company or the purpose of the office, there are a number of benefits to having the intercom professionally installed. Anderson (2014) views intercom as a security apparatus, according to the author, security is important wherever you work, from top security government sites through to small branch offices. An intercom system means entry can always be monitored, and is especially important if there is no formal reception area. If you only have one person on your reception desk, an intercom is a vital gateway that prevents malicious visitors or out of hours calls to the

company office.

Angel (2013) opines that a secure building is an attractive proposition to potential owners if it has a comprehensive intercom system in place. They can take ownership, move staff in and not have to worry about the safety of their employees. If the building is to be used as a facility for other purposes other than just staff - as a storage unit business for example - the cost savings are huge, and the efficiency gains considerably.

Statement of the Problem and Objectives of Study

Scholars in various past studies have linked satisfaction with workers' state of mind with their jobs. Whichever of the communication pattern an organization chooses, possesses the likelihood of affecting the satisfaction of its staff on their job and invariably the attainment of their organizational goals. It is against this backdrop that this study intends to investigate the influence of in-houses communication patterns on job satisfaction of library staff using Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri Imo State Nigeria as a case study.

The key objectives of the study are subsumed in the following research questions investigated:

- 1) What is the influence of memo on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria?
- 2) What is the influence of Newsletter on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri Imo State, Nigeria?
- 3) What are the influences of intercom on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria?

Methodology

The describe survey design was adopted for the study, using the questionnaire as the instrument for data collection in other to find out the influence of in-house communication patterns on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education Owerri, Nigeria. The population of the study is 73 (seventy three) library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education Owerri, Nigeria.

The questionnaire is titled In-House Communication Patterns on Job Satisfaction of Library Questionnaire (ICPJSLSQ). The face and content validity of the instrument was determined by experts in the Departments of Library and Information Science and Measurement and Evaluation.

No sample size was drawn from the population. This is because the population of the study is small and

accessible. The census method was used to ensure that opinions of all the staff in the library at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria were captured for the study.

Data Analysis

Seventy three copies of the questionnaire were given to library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Library Owerri, Nigeria. All were returned, giving a response rate of 100%. SPSS version 21 was used for analysis. The inclusion criteria was set at 2.50.

Results

Research Question 1

What is the influence of memo on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of

Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria?

Table 1 shows the influence of memo on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria. Communication through memo increases my job satisfaction ($x=1.88$), I do not derive satisfaction on my job because of how I am being communicated through memo ($x=2.19$), the more one is communicated through memo, the better understanding of the job ($x=2.04$) and finally frequent communication through memo attracts more pressure on the job ($x=2.34$). The above table had their means below cut-off point of 2.50. This confirms that memo has no influence on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria.

Table 1: Mean Value of the Influence of Memo on Job Satisfaction of Library Staff

S/N	Memo and Job Satisfaction	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
		4	3	2	1	
a	Communication through memo increases my job satisfaction	2	3	52	16	1.88
b	I do not derive satisfaction on my job because of how I am being communicated through memo	10	4	49	10	2.19
c	The more one is communicated through memo, the better understanding of the job	6	4	50	13	2.04
d	Frequent communication through memo attracts more pressure on the job	49	10	4	10	2.34
	Significant Mean Value					2.36

Research Question 2

What is the influence of Newsletter on job

satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri Imo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Value of the Influence of Newsletter on Job Satisfaction of Library Staff

S/N	Newsletter and Job Satisfaction	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
a	Newsletter keeps me informed on my job	44	19	6	4	3.41
b	I am not satisfied on my job owing to the fact that newsletter are not readily available in the library	6	2	53	12	2.02
c	Newsletter makes me more confident in service delivery	53	13	3	4	3.58
d	Newsletter makes my job clearer.	49	10	6	8	3.37
	Significant Mean Value					3.10

Table 2 shows the influence of newsletter on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Newsletter keeps me informed on my job ($x=3.41$) I am not satisfied on my job owing to the fact that newsletters are not readily available in the library ($x=2.02$), Newsletter makes me more confident in service delivery ($x=3.58$) and finally Newsletter makes my job clearer ($x=3.37$). From the questionnaire table, the above shows the significant

mean value of ($x=3.10$) which is above the cutoff point (2.50) which leads to their acceptance. This means that newsletter has influence on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria.

Research Question 3

What are the influences of intercom on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean Value of the Influence of Intercom on Job Satisfaction of Library Staff

S/N	Intercom and Job Satisfaction	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
a	Intercom reduces the office stress	46	23	3	1	3.56
b	Intercom communication makes me fear no duty (ies) on my job	7	5	33	28	1.42
c	Guarantees my satisfaction by enhancing communication on the job	57	10	3	3	3.66
d	I am not satisfied on my job due to ineffective intercom in the library	6	4	50	13	2.04
	Significant Mean Value					2.67

Table 3 shows the influence of intercom on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Intercom reduces the office stress ($x=3.56$), intercom communication makes me fear no duty (ies) on my job ($x=1.42$), Guarantees my satisfaction by enhancing communication on the job ($x=3.66$) and finally, I am not satisfied on my job due to ineffective intercom in the library ($x=2.04$). The table (3) shows the significant means value to be above the inclusion criteria of 2.50 which lead to acceptance.

This means that intercom has influence on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Nigeria.

Discussion

Evidence from Table 1 shows that memo do not influence job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. This is despite its acclaimed popularity and advantages such as inexpensiveness to create, and keeping of record of operations in digital and or hardcopy, among others (Sharma and Mohan, 2002). This finding is in agreement with Newman (2013), who posited that memos can only call people to action or broadcast a bit of timely news, however, they are not supposed to appear too frequently; otherwise it may eventually result in job dissatisfaction over time. It therefore implies that organisations while maximizing the advantages of official memos should equally be mindful of their potential adverse effect.

Official Newsletter was found to have positive influence on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. Murphy (2014), observed that newsletters are published (in hard or soft copies) to provide information of interest to members, users or employers. This could account for this positive influence. In addition to its interesting contents, its infrequency could be responsible for the interest that staff members have towards it. Whereas it has been found to have positive influence on job satisfaction, it cannot replace the memo which carries on time information and or instructions.

The Finding equally revealed that intercom has positive influence on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. This finding corroborates Meyer (2013) postulation that an office intercom is useful for effective and on-time communication within an organisation, whether they have regular visitors or they are a closed site. Angel (2013)), also agreed with the above assertion by positing that an organisation with comprehensive intercom system makes for positive job satisfaction.

Conclusion and Recommendation

On the bases of findings and discussion therefrom the study concludes that intercoms and Newsletters are the in-house communication patterns that have greater positive influence on job satisfaction of library staff at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education, Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. This could be true for other library establishments both nationally and in diaspora. The following are therefore recommended:

- Feedback of key stakeholders like management and staff members should regularly be taken on in-house communications methods to discover their influence on job satisfaction of staff members.
- The memo as an in-house communication pattern need to be reengineered for job satisfaction of library staff generally and specifically at Alvan Ikoku Federal College of Education Owerri, Imo state, Nigeria that works in the interests of both the employees as well as the management.
- A further study is needed to establish the reason/s behind low performance of memo as an in-house communication pattern both internationally and in Nigeria.
- An international comparative study is recommended with a view to corroborating/refuting the findings of this study.

Competing Interests

None of the authors received any external financial and or other subvention/assistances from individuals or parties in the course of this study that could be considered to amount to conflict of interest.

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